

With the support of:

Hate in digital media in Spain, 2023

Hatemia Project

Prepared by: Hatemia Team

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<https://www.hatemia.es/publicaciones/>

Project funded by:

Project implemented with the support of:

Hatemia Team

With the assistance of: possible

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Hatemia Overview

Nutrition Facts Valeur nutritive

Per 1 cup (250 mL) / par 1 tasse (250 mL)

Amount Teneur	% Daily Value % valeur quotidienne
Calories / Calories 80	
Fat / Lipides 0 g	0 %
Saturated / saturés 0 g + Trans / trans 0 g	0 %
Cholesterol / Cholestérol 0 mg	
Sodium / Sodium 115 mg	5 %
Carbohydrate / Glucides 12 g	4 %
Fibre / Fibres 0 g	0 %
Sugars / Sucres 11 g	
Protein / Protéines 9 g	
Vitamin A / Vitamine A	15 %
Vitamin C / Vitamine C	0 %
Calcium / Calcium	30 %
Iron / Fer	0 %
Vitamin D / Vitamine D	45 %

PASTEURISED / PASTEURISÉ

Project commencement: July 2021

End of project: June 2025

Facebook: January to June 2022

Platform X: January 2021 to May 2022

Web: January 2021 and June 2022

Data collection

The selection periods fluctuated based on the challenges of data collection posed by the media themselves (as seen in the Facebook case) and the discontinuation of the academic API for such tasks (case X).

Messages collected:
19,203,803

Messages processed
and analyzed:
9,778,857

Measures implemented for the advancement of the project:

El Mundo, ABC, La Vanguardia, El País, 20 Minutos

Hatemedias Hate Classification Methodology

The process of cleaning messages gathered from digital news media in Spain.

With the assistance of: possible

****Extraction Characteristics:****

Positive word count

- Negative word count
- Number of the most prevalent bigrams
- Number of user references
- Sentiment classification based on the "pysentimiento" library for Spanish.

Text cleanup:

- convert to lowercase
- Punctuation marks (¿?, ¡!, etc.)
- Numbers
- Extra blank spaces
- Characters with a length of less than 2 (e.g., "second B" removes the "B").
- Tokenization
- Lemmatization

Labeling messages utilized for algorithm development at Hatemedia

Responsible team:

Elias Said-Hung / UNIR

Julio Montero-Diaz / UNIR

- Max Römer Pieretti / UCJC
- Damaso Izquierdo / UNAV
- Alberto de Lucas / UNIR
- Two professionals engaged for labeling tasks.

N=1,100,742 messages collected in January 2021 n=324,395 unique messages tagged Date: February-April 2022

Hate/Non-Hate Classification Algorithm Model Development

With the assistance of:

Evaluated models

Gradient Boosting, Random Forest, Multi-Layer Perceptron, Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machine, Classification and Regression Trees

Conducted assessments

The models were assessed utilizing various train-test splits, specifically in the ratios of 90/10, 80/20, and 70/30.

Hyperparameter optimization.

Assessing model accuracy via accuracy_score to gauge the performance of various models.

Training models using balanced and unbalanced datasets

Debugged messages utilized for model evaluation.
9.778.857

Duration of development activities
September 2023 – March 2024

Final model

CART model, utilizing 90-10 training

Hate Intensity Classification Algorithm Model Development

With the assistance of: possible

Evaluated models

Gradient Boosting, Random Forest, MLP, Naive Bayes, SVM, CART, Roberto

Conducted assessments

The models were assessed utilizing various train-test splits, specifically in the ratios of 90/10, 80/20, and 70/30.

Hyperparameter optimization.

Assessing model accuracy via accuracy_score to gauge the performance of various models.

Training models using balanced and unbalanced datasets

Debugged messages utilized for model evaluation.
9.778.857

Duration of development activities
September 2023 – March 2024

Levels of hate intensity assessed:

- Uncivil communications (Intensity 1)
- Malicious and abusive communications (Intensity 2)
- Insulting communications (Intensity 3)
- Threatening communications (Intensity 4)

Final model

CART-ADASYN model, utilizing an 80-20 training split

Hate classification algorithm model design categorized by type

With the assistance of: possible

Evaluated models

Gradient Boosting, Random Forest, MLP, Naive Bayes, SVM, CART, Roberto

Conducted assessments

The models were assessed utilizing various train-test splits, specifically in the ratios of 90/10, 80/20, and 70/30.

Hyperparameter optimization.

Assessing model accuracy via accuracy_score to gauge the performance of various models.

Training models using balanced and unbalanced datasets

Debugged messages utilized for model evaluation.
9.778.857

The selection periods fluctuated based on the challenges of data collection posed by the media themselves (as seen in the Facebook case) and the discontinuation of the academic API for such tasks (case X).

Types of hatred considered:

- Misogyny.
- Sexual.
- Xenophobia.
- Ideological.
- Racism.
- Religious.
- General or indefinite.

Final model

Robertuito model utilizing the ASGD optimizer

Accuracy: 0.7691256830601093

Reporte de Clasificación:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.66	0.65	0.66	147
1	0.75	0.77	0.76	146
2	0.74	0.73	0.74	147
3	0.90	0.86	0.88	146
4	0.80	0.84	0.82	146
accuracy			0.77	732
macro avg	0.77	0.77	0.77	732
weighted avg	0.77	0.77	0.77	732

Integration and implementation of algorithms in the Hatemedia Hate Monitor

With the assistance of: possible

<https://monitordeodio.hatemedi.es/>

The classification of hate by intensity and type is based on the total number of messages identified as hate through the hate/non-hate algorithm.

Hate Monitor Advancement

Hate Monitor, Early Warning Index, and Dashboard

Active since April 2024

Developed with the assistance of:

The monitor collects daily data on:

Platform X (A random sample of 10,000 messages obtained through the Basic API)

Web platforms utilized for the project's development.

<https://monitordeodio.hatemedi.es/>

A Dashboard and Index (MELIN) is accessible for the early detection of hate (0-10 points).

Through the Dashboard, you will have the capability to view the data collected daily via the Monitor (currently undergoing testing and analysis for potential patenting).

<https://www.hatemedi.es/>

Developed from the MELIN Transfer Project, which received funding from UNIR.

(Development produced as an adjunct to Hatemedi)

Mapping Hatred in the Spanish News Media

Mapping of Hate in Digital News Media in Spain, 2021-2022

With the assistance of: possible

General

No hate Hate

No hate Hate

No hate Hate

No hate Hate

Messages have been cleaned and analyzed.
9778857

Total messages gathered

Messages gathered
19203803

Data collection timeframe

Facebook: January to June 2022
Platform X: January 2021 to May 2022
Web: January 2021 and June 2022

The selection periods fluctuated based on the challenges of data collection posed by the media themselves (as seen in the Facebook case) and the discontinuation of the academic API for such tasks (case X).

The predominant form of hate in digital news media

Types of hate propagated by users of digital media in Spain

With the assistance of: possible

35% of the analyzed hate messages are of a political nature.

30% of the analyzed hate messages are of a general nature, lacking a clear focus on a specific social group.

35% of the analyzed hate messages are categorized among the other types of hate addressed in this study.

General or undifferentiated hate:

Manifestations of hate that do not exhibit a distinct predominance of any specific type identified in this monitor.

Political hate:

Expressions directed towards individuals or groups based on their political affiliations.

Sexual Hate:

Hostile expressions aimed at individuals or groups based on their sexual orientation.

Misogynistic hate:

Manifestations aimed at women or characteristics linked to them.

Xenophobic hate:

Manifestations aimed at individuals or groups due to their origin (e.g., foreign nationals and immigrants).

Type of hate promoted based on support

Hostility fostered by digital media users in Spain

With the assistance of: possible

62.92% of the analyzed hate messages foster a climate of media hostility (intensity levels 1 and 2) towards vulnerable groups, such as women, immigrants, and the LGBTBI+ community.

37.05% of the analyzed hate messages foster a climate of media violence (intensity levels 3 and 4) directed at vulnerable groups, such as women, immigrants, and the LGBTBI+ community.

Media hostility refer to the promotion of feelings of anger, resentment and opposition, antagonistic or opposing attitudes towards a certain person or group, which can favour a more violent social framework (veiled or not), to cause harm to them (Walters & Espelage, 2020; Levin-Banchik, 2020; Kim, 2022). Hostility as a mediating factor of violence at a social level through comments published by digital news media (Quant et al., 2019)

Intent and climate of hate fostered in accordance with support

- Intensity 1** – Hostility linked to uncivil discourse
- Intensity 2** – Hatred linked to malicious messages or abusive expressions
- Intensity 3** – Hatred linked to insults
- Intensity 4** – Hatred characterized by implicit or overt threats

Profile of online detractors in Spain's digital media

With the assistance of: possible

Profile of online detractors in Spain's digital media

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Minority users, in contrast to others, engage in the discussions.

They seem to operate in a coordinated fashion across specific platforms (Facebook, X, or web portals).

Repeaters of ideas aim to shape narratives and concepts within public opinion.

Political actors, media representatives, and journalists are the primary targets of hate.

They employ news figures as actors who assist in portraying animosity directed towards members of social groups.

Media outlets with a pronounced ideological inclination towards "left" or "right" appear to be the primary recipients of engagement from this user demographic.

Several publications linked to the Hatemedia project

Said-Hung, E., Römer-Pieretti, M., Montero-Díaz, J., De Lucas Vicente, A., & Martínez Torres, J. (2023). Hate Speech Library in Spanish [Data set]. Hatemedia Project. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22383643>

De Lucas, A., Römer, M., Izquierdo, D., Montero-Díaz, J., & Said-Hung, E. (2023). Hate Message Labeling Manual. Hatemedia Project. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.18316313>

Said-Hung, E., Montero-Díaz, J., De Gregorio-Vicente, O., Ruiz-Iniesta, A., Blanco-Valencia, X., Cubillas-Market, J. J., & Perez, D. (2024). Hate detection algorithm in Spanish. Hatemedia Project. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.24574906>

De Gregorio-Vicente, O., Blanco-Valencia, X., Ruíz-Iniesta, A., Pérez, D., Cubillas-Mercado, J. J., Said-Hung, E., & Montero-Díaz, J. (2024). Technical report on the development of a hate/non-hate classification algorithm for Spanish digital news media on X (Twitter), Facebook, and web portals. Hatemedia Project. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.26085688>

Blanco-Valencia, X., Ruíz-Iniesta, A., Pérez, D., De Gregorio-Vicente, O., Cubillas-Mercado, J. J., Said-Hung, E., & Montero-Díaz, J. (2024). Algorithm for classifying hate speech by intensity in Spanish. Hatemedia Project. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25892815>

Blanco-Valencia, X., Ruíz-Iniesta, A., Pérez, D., De Gregorio-Vicente, O., Cubillas-Mercado, J., Said-Hung, E., & Montero-Díaz, J. (2024). Technical report on the development of an algorithm for classifying hate speech by intensity in Spanish digital news media on X (Twitter), Facebook, and web portals. Hatemedia Project. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25884262.v4>

Pérez Palau, D., Blanco-Valencia, X., Ruíz-Iniesta, A., De Gregorio-Vicente, O., Cubillas-Mercado, J., Said-Hung, E., & Montero-Díaz, J. (2024). Classification algorithm for hate speech by type in Spanish. Hatemedia Project. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25669038>

Pérez, D., Said-Hung, E., Blanco-Valencia, X., Ruíz-Iniesta, A., Cubillas-Mercado, J. J., & De Gregorio-Vicente, O. (2024). Technical report on the development of a hate classification algorithm by type in Spanish digital news media on X (Twitter), Facebook, and web portals. Hatemedia Project. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.26314360>

Arce-García, S., Said-Hung, E., & Montero-Díaz, J. (2024). Unmasking Coordinated Hate: Analyzing Hate Speech in Spanish Digital News Media. *New Media & Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448241259715>

Said-Hung, E., & Montero, J. (Eds.). (2023). News Media and Hate Speech Promotion in Mediterranean Countries. In *Advances in Media, Entertainment, and the Arts (AMEA) Book Series*. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-6684-8427-2>

Moreno, A., Said-Hung, E., & Römer Pieretti, M. (2024). *Hate Speech in Spanish Digital Contexts*. Tirant lo Blanch.

With the assistance of: possible

Thank you...

For further details regarding this project, please contact elias.said@unir.net.

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<https://www.hatemedias.es/>